

Mapping Dependencies and Prioritizations in Maritime Advanced Nuclear Reactor Integration using an Analytical Network Process

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Abstract. Reducing maritime greenhouse gas emissions and promoting alternatives to fossil fuels requires analysis of alternative energies, fuels, and technologies, many of which are novel in form or implementation. Advanced nuclear reactors, defined as reactors offering significantly improved safety, producibility, cost, and efficiency over existing reactor designs, represent one such technology area. Previous studies into integrating these technologies in marine platforms, including both ships and stationary platforms like power barges, focus primarily on identifying reactor designs suitable for maritime applications and their implementation. These studies do not consider reactor marinization as an aspect of the marine design process or esish dependencies between elements of reactor and marine vessel design. The presented research addresses this gap by mapping dependencies between the requirements underlying the designs of both the vessel and the reactor, along with the components of both systems. It uses the Analytical Network Process (ANP) to map and evaluate the network. The ANP employs initial pairwise comparisons of direct dependencies between network elements and subsequent matrix operations to map indirect dependencies, allowing it to account for mixed hierarchical and non-hierarchical network structures, such as a ship with a reactor as a subsystem. Dependency and prioritization judgments were established through a combination of evaluations by the authors with the results of a survey distributed to reactor designers and researchers. Weights were calculated for network elements for two design scenarios, considering the sensitivity of the network to varying design assumptions. This research contributes to developing a broader design methodology for parallel design of marine platforms and developing technologies like advanced reactors, enabling a broader initial design space and better-informed design decision-making.

Key words: *Maritime nuclear propulsion, Advanced nuclear reactors, Marine decarbonization, Systems integration, Analytical Network Process (ANP), Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), Marine systems engineering.*

1. Introduction

A range of new, “advanced” nuclear reactors, including molten salt reactors with dissolved fuels and modularized light-water reactors, introduce theoretical advantages over existing reactor designs in terms of safety, producibility, cost, and efficiency [1]. These reactors may have significant value for maritime applications amid concerns about climate change and energy security. Nuclear reactors have a history of use at sea, especially by the U.S. Navy, as well as the Russian, Chinese, and other navies. They have also been deployed in several commercial vessels – the N.S. Savannah (United States), Otto Hahn (Germany), and Mutsu (Japan), as well as a Russian nuclear power barge and eight nuclear icebreakers as of April 2025 [2, 3]. However, none of these commercial projects manifested on a wider scale due to a combination of factors, including public opposition to nuclear power, high costs, and concerns about nuclear proliferation risks. Even minor incidents like a small radiation release through the shielding of the Mutsu during reactor startup led to large scale public backlash [4]. The new generation of reactors mitigates many of these concerns. The result is a significantly renewed interest within the maritime industry in exploring the suitability of these new reactors for maritime applications. However, there are a multitude of different reactor concepts in development, each with uncertain maritime applicability. This uncertainty parallels challenges with

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integrating other emerging technologies — or radically novel and rapidly developing technologies with the potential for significant and uncertain impacts — into ship design [5]. Overcoming these challenges, stemming from a combination of uncertainty as to the eventual capabilities of the technologies and how they will interact with ship systems, requires methods and tools to facilitate understanding of design choices throughout the design process and collaboration between naval architects and reactor designers.

Most nuclear reactors currently in use at sea are pressurized water reactors (PWRs) [6]. PWRs operate in the thermal neutron energy range and use water to moderate and reflect neutrons, as well as to cool the reactor core. The water circulating through the reactor operates at a high pressure, enabling the water in the reactor to remain liquid even at high temperatures. Water's tendency to expand at high temperatures is also a self-stabilizing measure, as, if the reactor temperature increases, the water density will decrease, reducing its efficacy as both a reflector and moderator, and in turn reducing the reactor's criticality. Further, by using highly enriched fuels, naval PWRs are often able to operate without refueling for a decade or more [6]. Together, these factors make PWRs very well suited for naval operations. However, the same aspects that make these reactors advantageous for naval use disadvantage them for commercial maritime applications. Their high operating pressure brings with it the potential for a widespread dispersion of radioactive material in the event of a failure of the reactor's containment, in turn requiring very large emergency planning zones around the vessel [7]. Additionally, arms proliferation concerns prevent commercial ships from carrying large amounts of enriched fuel, meaning that nuclear commercial ships with PWRs would be subject to frequent refueling throughout their lifetime [6]. These challenges, along with issues of public perception after nuclear accidents like Chernobyl, have until now prevented large-scale commercial maritime nuclear implementation [8].

A range of reactors currently in development hold promise to address many of these challenges. Many of these reactors incorporate fuel deployments like tri-structural isotropic (TRISO) fuels and dissolved molten fuel salts that offer a range of potential benefits, including increased barriers to proliferation and passive safety features [1, 9]. In particular, TRISO fuel is self-contained, reducing the risk of release of fission products in case of a containment failure, while the use of molten fuel salts permits the use of dump tanks as a control mechanism for emergency conditions to stop the fission process. Other features, including the deployment of new cooling and control mechanisms, combine to give these advanced reactors a range of potential safety advantages compared to existing reactors, including improved negative temperature and radioactivity feedback, increased safety margins, and lower operating pressures. These features reduce the likelihood and potential severity of hazards involving the reactor and help to address many of the concerns surrounding PWRs. Further, many of these designs offer potentially increased efficiency and fuel burnup, enabling longer operation at a lower fuel enrichment [1]. However, these advanced reactors, generally still in the early stages of development, are largely untested in a marine environment, which introduces uncertain impacts from ship motions, along with a range of external and environmental hazards [10, 11]. It is unclear which reactors are best suited for this hostile environment, or how maritime platforms powered by nuclear reactors might operate [12].

Typical ship design, in seeking to address a specific set of objectives or requirements, takes a requirements-first, or "demand-pull" approach to such integration challenges, where demand drives technological development and design decision-making. As such, when selecting a power plant, ship designers usually design a propulsion architecture based on the operating profile that the ship is expected to operate under, and subject to the broad envelope of the vessel itself. Most existing shipboard nuclear reactor integration research follows this model. For instance, in a 2022 thesis, Hagen investigated the feasibility of nuclear power in maritime applications by performing case studies on a concept container ship transiting between Los Angeles, U.S.A, and Shanghai, China. Hagen considered a range of reactor technologies and selected a liquid-metal fast reactor based on its ability to meet the needs of the case study vessel [13].

Emblemsvåg et al. sought to more broadly identify reactors suitable for maritime use – a wider range of applications than a container route – but still utilized a requirements-first approach, proposing an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) subject to selection criteria prioritizing broad applicability to the maritime field to select a reactor design [12]. This research could help reactor designers and researchers identify a more limited selection of concepts for deeper consideration, and perhaps to subsequently guide marine design to adapt to a more limited set of possible reactor solutions.

Product design research – albeit focusing on simpler systems than ships – suggests that a “technology-

push” approach, letting the technology influence the design’s capabilities, may be more effective at promoting innovation [14]. Such an approach seems especially applicable to the case of the advanced nuclear reactors, given the uncertainties surrounding their implementation and capabilities in the maritime domain. Designing a vessel to accommodate the reactors might make otherwise infeasible solutions work for maritime applications. At the same time, down-selecting between reactors too early, before understanding the maritime potential or integration challenges of many of the concepts under consideration, risks eliminating potential reactor solutions that could be adapted for maritime use, or focusing too early on an option that subsequent studies and analysis may reveal unsuitable. Given the early status of many reactor concept designs, there is an opportunity for a parallel design process, allowing the ship and reactor ecosystems to influence each other rather than forcing one to conform to the other. Such an approach, especially if it can adapt to reflect new knowledge about the design space and resulting new design assumptions, may help to expand the feasible solution space and enable better-informed decision-making.

Network approaches are well-suited to such an exploration because of their ability to track both adjacency and dependence. In particular, a network showing the connections between the ship and reactor systems would offer significant value in understanding the implications of design decisions. Network methods are not novel to ship design, in particular to describe how elements of the design interact with each other [15]. However, a significant challenge to developing such a network for the ship-reactor interface is the same lack of understanding that drives it; there are no data points to use to guide a quantitative analysis of dependence, highlighting a need for comparative methods to inform decision-making. Saaty, the developer of the AHP that Emblemståg et al. are implementing, developed a broader Analytical Network Process (ANP) to allow feedback between network elements, while incorporating pairwise comparisons to quantify qualitative assessments of preference and dependence in the network [16]. This process is well-suited to understanding the dependencies in the ship-reactor combined system, and has the additional potential to provide weights and priorities for components that can guide future decision-making.

The ANP has been applied to many similar types of problems, with complex inter-dependencies. It was used by Akyuz in 2015 to assess navigational contingencies to prevent ship groundings, considering a system wherein decisions could influence each other’s effects [17]. It was similarly applied by Hosseini et al. to select a strategy to reduce supply chain risks, permitting consideration of a complex network of dependencies between different types of risks [18].

This paper presents the development of an ANP approach towards understanding the interface between the ship and reactor systems and identifying design priorities to guide the design process during the development of both systems. It focuses on an abstraction of the overall interface, based on two ship characteristics that have repeatedly appeared in research as key concerns for reactor integration: ship motions and threats to the ship from external events, such as attacks or environmental hazards. It additionally investigates the ability of the ANP method to adapt to changes in assumptions about the interface or its surrounding design space. The method was developed such that it could be expanded to consider the broader interface, and its findings used for subsequent design decision-making.

2. Method

The ANP requires a network of direct connections between nodes, called elements, grouped into clusters based on their respective roles in the network. The ANP can include both physical components considered in the decision-making process, such as design alternatives, as well as criteria or requirements [16]. In other words, the network is not just a representation of the technology under consideration, but also of how that technology interacts with the decision.

$$[W] = \begin{matrix} & & & C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \\ & & & e_{11} e_{12} \dots e_{1m} & e_{21} e_{22} \dots e_{2m} & & e_{n1} e_{n2} \dots e_{nm} \\ C_1 & e_{11} & & & & & \\ & e_{12} & & & & & \\ & \vdots & & & & & \\ & e_{1m} & & & & & \\ C_2 & e_{21} & & & & & \\ & e_{22} & & & & & \\ & \vdots & & & & & \\ & e_{2m} & & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & & & \\ & e_{n1} & & & & & \\ C_n & e_{n2} & & & & & \\ & \vdots & & & & & \\ & e_{nm} & & & & & \end{matrix}$$

Figure 1: The ANP supermatrix [16].

The primary utility of the ANP is its ability to deconstruct a decision into many smaller evaluations. The ANP takes these evaluations – the direct importance of elements on the network on each other – and maps them to their general influence within the network, similarly to measures of centrality from network theory. The first stage of the ANP, then, is to construct a matrix showing the direct linkages between elements. This matrix, called a supermatrix, is described in Figure 1 [16].

Each W_{ij} is a smaller sub-matrix describing the influence of the row elements $e_{i1}, e_{i2}, \dots, e_{im}$ on column elements $e_{j1}, e_{j2}, \dots, e_{jm}$ in Figure 1. The importance of row elements for each column element of Figure 1 is determined relative to the other elements in its cluster [16]. Consider if it were determined that elements e_{11}, e_{12} , and e_{13} all influence element e_{31} , and e_{11}, e_{12} , and e_{13} were all in the same cluster. Pairwise comparisons are performed between each of e_{11}, e_{12} , and e_{13} regarding their relative influence on element e_{31} according to the scale in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Saaty’s fundamental scale [16].

Figure 3 depicts a square reciprocal matrix describing this process for e_{11}, e_{12} , and e_{13} relative to element e_{31} (i.e., Cluster W_{11} on e_{13}). The main diagonal of the matrix in Figure 3 is filled with values of “1” because an element cannot have more influence on element e_{31} than itself. So cell 1,2 describes how much more important element e_{11} is than element e_{12} in terms of its influence on e_{31} , and so on for the top half of the matrix. Fractional values are used to describe the cases where e_{11} is less important. The bottom half contains the reciprocal of these values, so cell 2,1 describes how much more important element e_{12} is than e_{11} .

e_{31}	e_{11}	e_{12}	e_{13}
	1	2	3
e_{11}	1		
e_{12}		1	
e_{13}			1

Figure 3: Pairwise comparison matrix [16].

The relative weights of each element in the cluster are determined by finding the principal eigenvector of the matrix and normalizing it to sum to one. This step also enables the determination of the consistency of the comparisons with regard to each other. A consistency index, CI , is defined as:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of comparisons and λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the matrix. A matrix is considered consistent if its Consistency Ratio (CR) — the ratio of its CI to the average CI derived from a large sample of randomly generated equally sized reciprocal matrices — is less than 0.1. Otherwise, the evaluations are reviewed to identify inconsistent judgments. Eigenvector weights based on inconsistent judgments are considered invalid [16].

These relative weights are incorporated into a supermatrix, called the unweighted supermatrix. An additional step is required to transform this matrix for subsequent use in the ANP process. Each column of the unweighted supermatrix contains values that sum to 1 only within their respective clusters rather than across the entire column. ANP requires a column stochastic matrix where each column itself sums to 1. To produce this transformation, another set of pairwise comparisons is first performed, this time between the clusters themselves in terms of their influence on each other. Then, the row elements are scaled based on the relative weight of their cluster and normalized, ensuring that the matrix will be column stochastic. The result of this process is the weighted supermatrix [16].

An example set of comparisons between clusters is shown in Figure 4, which depicts sample pairwise comparisons according to the Saaty scale for the relative influence of clusters C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 on cluster C_1 . This study investigates using these weights as a toggle to apply different assumptions about the system integration to the network. This is separate from sensitivity analyses in ANP, which generally consider perturbations to a node or its associated interactions [19]. Two case studies were performed to investigate this approach. Case 1, a demand-pull case, used a ship-centric design approach that prioritized meeting requirements for the ship design. Case 2, a technology-push case, assumed a relatively fixed reactor design had been pre-selected. In both cases, it was assumed that these design objectives did not contravene the requirement that the system would be safe and be designed subject to defense-in-depth principles. These assumptions were accounted for within the cluster-weighting pairwise comparison process.

C_1	C_1	C_2	C_3
	1	2	3
C_1	1	3	1/5
C_2	1/3	1	7
C_3	5	1/7	1

Figure 4: Example of cluster pairwise comparisons [16].

After being weighted by multiplying by the eigenvectors of the cluster comparisons, the supermatrix is raised to the power of n , where n is an arbitrarily large power. This process ensures that the matrix captures indirect connections in the network. The outcome of this process will be the weights of elements in the network, relative to their influence on the rest of the network, making this method ideally suited to understanding a problem such as the interface between two highly complex systems, for instance, between a ship and a nuclear reactor [16].

It is possible that, at this phase, $[W]^n$ will differ from $[W]^{n+1}$, before, after being raised to i additional powers, returning to the form of $[W]^n$. If this cycling behavior is observed, the average of the variations is used for the limit supermatrix [16].

This study used a network composed of four clusters: two decision-making clusters and two component clusters. Table 1 describes the clusters used and the definitions of their respective elements. While the clusters are representative of the ship-reactor interface, a limited subset of their total elements was used in this study to demonstrate the approach while reducing the number of comparisons that would need to be performed within the scope of the research. Specifically, this study focuses on only three performance metrics of the ship – its vulnerability to external hazards, its susceptibility to motions, and the power demanded by the vessel.

Due to the complexity of the interface between the ship and reactor systems, a survey was distributed to researchers, regulators, and members of the nuclear industry interacting with different aspects of the interface to perform pairwise comparisons regarding the interactions between the ship performance and reactor component clusters. The geometric mean of the responses was used to determine local priorities. The authors determined the priorities for the remainder of the network based on existing knowledge and standard assumptions about the respective designs of ships and reactors. After weighting the supermatrix, the global priorities of the network elements were determined using the ANP process.

Table 1: Cluster and element definitions.

Cluster	Element	Definition
Ship Performance Metrics	External Hazard Vulnerability	The likelihood that damage from external hazards to the ship like collisions, allisions, or groundings will result in non operability or unsafe conditions of the system (ship + reactor). Examples of damage from these hazards are direct impulse forces against components or transferred impacts via deformation of other components, failures of components elsewhere in the system, fires, and flooding.
	Motions Susceptibility	Vessel ability to continue to operate while experiencing accelerations of varying magnitudes, frequencies, and directions, or inclinations to various angles along any degree of freedom, occurring during normal operation (i.e. design conditions) of the ship and reactor systems.
	Power Demand	The power demanded to move the vessel and by any and all ship systems or mission capabilities.
Ship Components	Hull Shape	Choices about the physical shape of the ship's hull.
	Structure	The global and local structural elements that make up the ship.
	Power Generation & Propulsion	The architectures contributing propelling the ship and satisfying its hotel loads and other power demands, including turbines or other engines, generators, motors, gearboxes, and busses.
Reactor Performance Metrics	Space	The physical space the reactor takes up in the ship, including of both the containment around the core, as well as of any reactor systems outside the containment.
	Weight	The weight of the reactor system, including of the elements of the core and heat transfer mechanisms, the containment and shielding around the core, as well as of any reactor systems outside the containment.
	Disruption Tolerance / Availability	The ability of the reactor to continue to operate without causing any hazards for the ship, its personnel, societ, or the environment after a disruption occurs to any of its systems, including physical damage, malfunction, or component wear.
	Design Power Output	The power output by the reactor core, before being transferred to electrical or mechanical power by generators in the ship's power & propulsion systems.
Reactor Components	Core Configuration	The materials and design of the physical entity producing self-sustaining fission reactions, not including cooling or control systems. This includes the fuel, reflector, any moderator, and necessary structural materials that impact neutronic considerations.
	Core Cooling System	Any pumps, pipes, or other structures necessary for heating/cooling the core, maintaining reactor operating temperatures, and transmitting thermal power to external electrical/mechanical power conversion devices.
	Shielding & Containment	Any mechanisms or components that protect the reactor from external factors or contain the release of radioactive materials in the event of an accident, as well as the radiation shielding necessary to protect operators and external systems.
	Reactivity Control	The mechanisms whose sole or supplementary purpose is the adjustment of reactor criticality, such as control rods, drums, or poisons.

3. Application of the ANP to the Ship-Reactor Interface and Results

The network investigated in this study is shown in Figure 5. Arrows indicate pathways of influence between elements in the network. Elements are grouped with other elements in their clusters. Initial assignments of influence shown in Figure 5 were made by the authors, and any perceived possibility of influence was assumed to mean that an influence existed. Directions of influence are shown with arrows. A bidirectional arrow means that both elements influence each other directly, whereas a unidirectional path indicates that only one element influences the other.

Figure 5: Abstraction of the ship-reactor influence directed network.

This setup, using both components and performance metrics for each system, allows evaluators to understand the factors influencing their system of specialization without understanding the specific components of the other system – essentially, the performance metrics act as an intermediary between systems, avoiding the need to directly evaluate component-to-component influence. Further, these metrics, once weighted by their importance in the system through the ANP process, will provide insight into the value of targeting different metrics towards the performance of the overall design.

As described in the key in Figure 5, comparisons performed as part of the survey are marked in orange and pertain to the relationships between ship performance metrics and reactor components. Evaluations relating to other aspects of the network were performed by the authors. This network describes only direct influence between elements, and does not consider indirect influence at this stage – for instance, the configuration of the reactor influences the physical space required for the reactor, which then influences the design of the vessel hull to accommodate the reactor – but the core configuration has no direct influence on the hull design, only influencing it indirectly through the “size” performance metric of the reactor. These indirect influences are accounted for later in the ANP process.

Pairwise comparisons were performed for elements in each pairing of clusters indicated in the network. When bi-directional influence was present, both directions of influence (i.e., reactor components on ship performance, and ship components on reactor performance) were evaluated. Eigenvectors and consistency ratios were determined for each cluster pairing to determine local priorities. For instance, Table 2 illustrates the influence of ship components on the ship performance metric “Power Demand”, and Table 3 the influence of ship performance metrics on the ship component “Hull Shape”. In the case of Table 2, only one comparison is performed because it was determined that the choice of power generation architecture and the structural design of the vessel would not notably influence the hull design of the vessel. Meanwhile, three comparisons were required for the impact on hull shape because it was determined that all three of the performance metrics considered would influence hull shape. In each case, evaluations were performed from a design decision-making standpoint, meaning that they were assumed to be technology agnostic.

The resulting eigenvectors were inputted into the unweighted supermatrix described in Table 8 as representations of local influence within the network. Pairwise comparisons for ship-to-ship evaluations were

guided by several ship design principles. In particular, the importance of components on performance metrics was characterized in terms of direct relevance. For instance, the structural design of the vessel directly relates to its vulnerability to external hazards, whereas power generation systems, while of importance due to aspects like redundancies and tolerance to large accelerations, are less directly involved. Additionally, consideration was given to the difficulty of alternative pathways to reach a given performance metric. For instance, if a given propulsion system has a higher center of gravity, which would impact the extent of motions the ship experiences, it might be possible to alter the hull design or even add ballast. Meanwhile, the consequences of an unseaworthy hull shape would be much more difficult to rectify with alterations to other attributes of the ship. The same method was used to compare the influence of the reactor performance metrics on ship components. For instance, the thermal power output by the reactor will have a direct impact on how the propulsion and electrical architectures are designed, whereas the size of the reactor would only have tangential impacts if it limits the available space for power generation systems.

Similarly, on the reactor side, the attributes of each component were considered with regard to their impacts on the reactor’s performance. For instance, because most of the space occupied by reactor designs consists of shielding and containment, whereas the size of the core itself is small by comparison, the space required for the reactor was evaluated as being much more dependent on shielding and containment than on the choice of core configuration.

Power Demand	Hull Shape	Eigenvector
Hull Shape	1	1

Table 2: Influence of ship components on ship power demand. This matrix is inherently consistent.

Hull Shape	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand
External Hazard Vulnerability	1	1/5 -- Larger dimensions allow more room for structure, but motions performance is directly driven by hull shape. A larger vessel may also be a bigger target.	1/5 -- Power demand requirements / constraints can rapidly limit hull shape options, whereas vulnerabilities will indirectly expand structural options.
Motions Susceptibility	5	1	1 -- Tradeoffs between two major drivers of hull shape.
Power Demand	5	1	1

Table 3: Influence of ship performance metrics on hull shape (CR = 0.000).

The influences of performance metrics on components, internally to both systems, as well as of reactor performance on ship components, were evaluated in terms of the extent to which they would influence decisions about components. For instance, when considering a tradeoff between increased size and failing to meet power requirements in terms of the design of the core configuration, power output would be prioritized, as it pertains to the primary purpose of the reactor, even as the space required for the reactor would retain some influence over the design due to its influence on the functionality of the plant overall. More detailed breakdowns of these comparisons are provided in the appendix.

A survey was distributed to nuclear reactor designers, researchers, regulators, and manufacturers. Eleven complete responses were collected. Two responses were excluded because the respondents communicated misunderstandings of the questions posed in the survey in communications to the authors. The backgrounds of the remaining nine respondents are shown in Table 4. Of the respondents who indicated “other” as their background in Table 4, one indicated being involved in manufacturing, and another a designer with nuclear regulatory experience. One did not indicate an alternate background.

Table 4: Backgrounds of Survey Respondents.

Background	Percent	Number of Respondents
Nuclear Industry	78%	7
Maritime Industry	33%	3
Governmental	11%	1
Energy Sector	33%	3
Research & Development	33%	3
Regulator	22%	2
Academia	22%	2
Other	33%	3

The survey findings are shown in Tables 5 through 7, along with geometric means and standard deviations for each comparison. The geometric mean of responses for each comparison was inputted into a corresponding pairwise comparison matrix and the corresponding eigenvector was determined. These tables were transformed into pairwise comparison matrices, and eigenvectors were determined as with the comparisons performed by the authors.

Table 5: Survey results for influence on vulnerability to external hazards.

Option 1	Core Configuration	Core Configuration	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Shielding & Containment
Option 2	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control	Reactivity Control
Option 1 Extremely More Important: 9	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	1	0	0
5	0	2	0	2	4	3
3	1	1	2	1	1	0
Equal Importance: 1	4	1	4	2	3	3
1/3	0	0	1	2	1	1
1/5	3	5	2	1	0	2
1/7	1	0	0	0	0	0
Option 2 Extremely More Important 1/9	0	0	0	0	0	0
Geometric Mean	0.53	0.66	0.79	1.31	2.04	1.06
Standard Deviation	2.75	4.08	2.61	3.56	2.59	3.50

Table 6: Survey results for influence on motions susceptibility.

Option 1	Core Configuration	Core Configuration	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Shielding & Containment
Option 2	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control	Reactivity Control
Option 1 Extremely More Important: 9	0	1	0	1	0	0
7	0	3	1	1	0	0
5	3	0	0	3	3	0
3	0	0	1	0	0	2
Equal Importance: 1	1	5	2	2	3	1
1/3	1	0	2	2	1	2
1/5	4	0	2	0	1	1
1/7	0	0	1	0	1	2
Option 2 Extremely More Important 1/9	0	0	0	0	0	1
Geometric Mean	0.74	2.44	0.62	2.12	1.02	0.43
Standard Deviation	1.90	1.56	1.76	1.74	1.79	1.72

Table 7: Survey results for influence of reactor components on ship performance.

Influence On	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
External Hazard Vulnerability Extremely More Important: 9	0	0	0	0
7	2	1	2	1
5	2	3	3	3
3	0	3	2	1
Equal Importance: 1	0	0	2	0
1/3	2	0	0	1
1/5	3	1	0	3
1/7	0	1	0	0
Motions Extremely More Important 1/9	0	0	0	0
Geometric Mean	1.01	2.06	3.36	1.24
Standard Deviation	4.94	3.93	2.03	4.66

The results of these comparisons, along with the evaluations performed by the authors, were assembled into the unweighted supermatrix in Table 8.

Comparisons were performed between clusters to construct the weighted supermatrix. These comparisons were performed twice, subject to differing assumptions in the design case studies. Under the demand-pull framework of Case 1 (Ship Requirements-pull), satisfying ship performance requirements was the key objective, and it was assumed that the ship-reactor system would be designed subject to the objective of satisfying those requirements. These assumptions are reflected in the comparisons in several ways. For instance, under the assumption that the primary design objective was to design a ship to meet a set of requirements, the reactor was treated as a component in the ship and weighted relative to other components. Ship performance was considered the driving influence on ship components, and of equal influence relative to reactor components in controlling reactor performance – only as an objective instead of a constraint. A baseline safety assumption was maintained in that the system would still have to be designed to ensure the safety of the crew and public from the reactor, meaning that reactor systems were still evaluated as having a significant influence on each other. The resulting comparisons and eigenvectors are shown in Table 9.

In the technology-push framework of Case 2 (Reactor Technology-push), it was assumed that the reactor design was pre-selected and that alterations to the design would be vastly more costly to implement than changes to the ship system. In comparisons with the influence of ship components, reactor components were weighted as having increased influence because of the difficulty of alteration. Ship performance was similarly devalued in comparisons relative to the demand-pull case because ship performance was not set as an objective or constraint in the Case 2 assumptions, instead acting as a reflection of the performance of the system as a whole. The comparisons and eigenvectors for Case 2 are shown in Table 10.

In both cases, interactions where the assumptions corresponding to each case shifted the results of the comparison, either towards increased ship or increased reactor influence, are indicated in blue and red, respectively. These cases function as the extreme ends of the feasible space, offering insight into the network’s sensitivity to differing design assumptions.

Table 8: Unweighted supermatrix.

	Ship Performance			Ship Components			Reactor Performance			Reactor Components				
	Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Ship Performance														
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.09	0.79	0.18	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.67	0.77	0.55
Motions Susceptibility	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.15	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.33	0.23	0.45
Power Demand	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.07	0.75	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ship Components														
Hull Shape	0.08	0.78	1.00	0.00	0.83	1.00	0.88	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Structure	0.73	0.11	0.00	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Power Generation	0.19	0.11	0.00	0.17	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Space	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	0.17	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.09	0.05	0.64
Weight	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.17	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.10
Availability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.39	0.73	0.26
Design Power	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.39	0.73	0.26
Output	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.47	0.16	0.00
Reactor Performance														
Core Configuration	0.17	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.13	0.15	0.46	0.00	0.62	0.75	0.75
Heat Exchange Mechanism	0.36	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.57	0.57	0.13	0.22	0.07	0.00	0.13	0.21
Shielding & Containment	0.25	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.27	0.05	0.00	0.42	0.09	0.00	0.04
Reactivity Control	0.21	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.04	0.67	0.32	0.51	0.30	0.12	0.00

Ship Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	1/7	1/3	1/3	0.07	0.00
Ship Components	7	1	3	3	0.55	
Reactor Performance	3	1/3	1	1	0.19	
Reactor Components	3	1/3	1	1	0.19	
Ship Components	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	5	5		0.71	0.00
Ship Components	1/5	1	1		0.14	
Reactor Performance	1/5	1	1		0.14	
Reactor Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	5	1		0.44	0.01
Ship Components	1/5	1	1/7		0.08	
Reactor Components	1	7	1		0.49	
Reactor Components	Ship Performance	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR	
Ship Performance	1	1/5	3	0.19	0.06	
Reactor Performance	5	1	7	0.73		
Reactor Components	1/3	1/7	1	0.08		

Table 9: Case 1, Requirements-pull – Cluster weights assuming objective to satisfy ship requirements. Blue indicates comparisons where assumptions were of substantial influence.

Ship Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	1/7	1/5	1/5	0.06	0.01
Ship Components	7	1	1	1	0.33	
Reactor Performance	5	1	1	1	0.31	
Reactor Components	5	1	1	1	0.31	
Ship Components	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	5	1		0.45	0.00
Ship Components	1/5	1	1/5		0.09	
Reactor Performance	1	5	1		0.45	
Reactor Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR
Ship Performance	1	1	1/9		0.09	0.00
Ship Components	1	1	1/9		0.09	
Reactor Components	9	9	1		0.82	
Reactor Components	Ship Performance	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components	Eigenvector	CR	
Ship Performance	1	1/9	1/5	0.06	0.02	
Reactor Performance	9	1	3	0.67		
Reactor Components	7	1/7	1	0.26		

Table 10: Case 2, Technology-push – Cluster weights assuming reactor design is mostly fixed. Red indicates comparisons where assumptions were of substantial influence.

These evaluations for each case were used to weight the clusters of the unweighted supermatrix. The resulting weighted supermatrices for Cases 1 and 2, after re-normalization to ensure the matrix was column stochastic, are shown in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

The weighted supermatrices for both cases, S_1 and S_2 respectively, were raised to high powers until they converged with the Euclidean norm of the difference between S_i^n and S_i^{n-1} less than 10^{-6} . This occurred at $n = 40$ for Case 1 and at $n = 33$ for Case 2. The resulting limit supermatrices for Cases 1 and 2 are shown in Tables 13 and 14, respectively, and describe the final weights for each element in the network. No cycling was observed in either case, and weights could be determined in both cases. Tables 15 and 16 show the final weights of the components and performance metrics, respectively, in Cases 1 and 2, re-normalized within their clusters.

Table 11: Weighted supermatrix for Case 1 (Requirements-pull) — Note that it is column stochastic.

	Ship Performance			Ship Components			Reactor Performance			Reactor Components				
	External Hazard	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Ship Performance														
External Hazard	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.06	0.56	0.13	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.13	0.15	0.10
Vulnerability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.11	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.06	0.04	0.08
Motions Susceptibility	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.05	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Power Demand	0.05	0.46	0.89	0.00	0.12	0.14	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hull Shape	0.43	0.07	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Structure														
Ship Components														
Power Generation	0.11	0.07	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Space	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.07	0.04	0.47
Weight	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.02	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.08
Availability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.29	0.54	0.19
Reactor Performance														
Design Power Output	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.26	0.34	0.11	0.00
Reactor Components														
Core Configuration	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	0.08	0.22	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.06
Heat Exchange Mechanism	0.08	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.49	0.07	0.11	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02
Shielding & Containment	0.05	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.23	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
Reactivity Control	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.35	0.16	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.00
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 12: Weighted supermatrix for Case 2 (Technology-push) — Note that it is column stochastic.

	Ship Performance			Ship Components			Reactor Performance			Reactor Components				
	Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Ship Performance														
External Hazard	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.04	0.56	0.08	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.03
Vulnerability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.07	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.03
Motions Susceptibility	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.03	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Power Demand	0.03	0.27	0.86	0.00	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hull Shape	0.26	0.04	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Structure														
Ship Components														
Power Generation	0.07	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Space	0.32	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.08	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.43
Weight	0.00	0.32	0.00	0.08	0.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.07
Availability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.26	0.49	0.17
Design Power Output	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.32	0.11	0.00
Reactor Performance														
Core Configuration	0.06	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.11	0.13	0.38	0.00	0.16	0.20	0.20
Heat Exchange Mechanism	0.12	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.51	0.12	0.18	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.05
Shielding & Containment	0.08	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.23	0.24	0.04	0.00	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.01
Reactivity Control	0.07	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.60	0.26	0.14	0.08	0.03	0.00
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 13: Final converged weights for Case 1 (Requirements-pull).

	Ship Performance			Ship Components			Reactor Performance			Reactor Components				
	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Ship Performance	0.13	0.08	0.12	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.13	0.08	0.12	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
Motions Susceptibility	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.08	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.08
Power Demand	0.12	0.17	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.12	0.12	0.12
Ship Components	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Motions Susceptibility	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
Power Demand	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Reactor Performance	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Design Power Output	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Reactor Components	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Configuration	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Heat Exchange Mechanism	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07
Reactor Components	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Shielding & Containment	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Reactivity Control	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 14: Final converged weights for Case 2 (Technology-push).

	Ship Performance			Ship Components			Reactor Performance			Reactor Components				
	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Ship Performance	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Motions Susceptibility	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Power Demand	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Ship Components	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Structure	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Power Generation	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Reactor Performance	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
Weight	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Availability	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
Reactor Components	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
Configuration	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
Heat Exchange Mechanism	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
Reactor Components	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
External Hazard Vulnerability	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Shielding & Containment	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14
Reactivity Control	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14
SUM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 15: Final converged component weights for both cases.

Component	Ship Components			Reactor Components			
	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Requirements-pull	0.59	0.31	0.10	0.21	0.37	0.18	0.25
Technology-push	0.61	0.25	0.15	0.28	0.27	0.14	0.31

Table 16: Final converged performance weights for both cases.

Performance Metric	Ship Performance Metrics			Reactor Performance Metrics			
	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output
Requirements-pull	0.40	0.24	0.36	0.37	0.18	0.27	0.18
Technology-push	0.42	0.23	0.34	0.32	0.10	0.35	0.22

4. Discussion

The objective of this study was to apply the ANP method to account for inter-dependencies within the ship-reactor interface, in order to identify design priorities for performance metrics and system elements of both the ship and reactor. For the limited abstraction of the interface considered, weights were determined for demand-pull and technology-push design cases, giving priorities within the network and identifying the most important performance metrics to target with design decisions, shown in Table 16. These priorities can be applied to rank alternatives in a decision-making process or to set weights in various optimization approaches, including for a multi-objective Pareto front.

Figures 6 and 7 display the full weighted networks for both cases. Edges reflect direct weighted connections between elements in the network (not accounting for indirect connections), while nodes are sized according to the weights determined by the ANP process.

Notably, there is a marked difference in both the strength of direct connections emanating from certain nodes — for example, the node "Weight" in the requirements-pull case — and in the overall importance of the nodes themselves. In this case, "Hull Shape" received a weight of 0.17, making it the most influential node. This result reflects its key influence on both power demand and motions, which in turn enables it to interact indirectly with much of the system. Here, hull shape serves as the primary driver for meeting ship requirements, independent of the reactor. Consequently, the reactor would likely be developed subject to constraints imposed by the hull shape. In contrast, in the technology-push case, the weight of hull shape decreases to 0.05, while the reactor's components and their collective performance become the primary drivers. This shift reflects the constraints imposed by pre-selecting a reactor and logically implies that, under these circumstances, the reactor will constrain the overall ship design.

This occurrence offers insight into the sensitivity of the network and suggests that these nodes function effectively to route other connections, and are dominant for their indirect, as opposed to direct, connections. The ability of the ANP to capture this information is significant because solely considering local direct influences between elements would not offer insight into the importance of these elements within the system. There are large differences between the networks corresponding to the two design case studies, as well as in the final weights determined through the ANP process and shown in Tables 13 and 14, while the local importance of the weights after the ANP process, shown in Tables 15 and 16, remains largely unchanged. This result suggests that indirect connections, influenced by the application of global weights, do not override the relative local prioritization within a cluster. In other words, normal design priorities for a ship and reactor do not substantially change in this network, even as their importance relative to the priorities of the whole system adapts to the application of new assumptions and constraints applied to the system.

Figure 6: Directed network of direct influence for the demand-pull case (Case 1) — Nodes scaled by ANP weights. Visualization generated using Gephi software [20].

This study presents a novel implementation of the ANP that may have value for other systems integration projects involving early-stage design decision-making beyond this particular interface. This implementation, in linking components of different systems through metrics describing their performance, enables the division of the network such that pairwise comparisons performed for impacts on each system can be performed specifically by experts specializing in that system, even if they are not familiar with the broader interface. Further, the application of global weights functions as a toggle to adjust the network to reflect different design assumptions. This adjustability suggests an additional application for the ANP – to understand how changes to assumptions about the systems or their interactions impact the design space.

Two primary limitations applied to this study. First, adding additional elements to the network rapidly increases the number of comparisons required. To reduce the length of the survey, a significant simplification of the broader ship-reactor interface was used. While the priorities are valid relative to each other, they do not give insight into how they would fit within the complete interface. The addition of other priorities could also lead decision-makers to alter prioritizations or even reverse their judgments. Additionally, only nine participants took the survey. This limited sample size reduces confidence in the weights determined by the survey, especially given the very large standard deviations present in the results. This variance suggests the final weights may not be immediately applicable to future design work. Multiple factors may have led to this variance in responses, including unfamiliarity with the pairwise-comparison survey method or an overemphasis by the respondents on the particular type of reactor they are used to working with when considering their responses. While the survey sought general insights, two respondents communicated that they had responded to the survey based on their experience with a particular type of reactor. Although responses that indicated an incorrect interpretation of the survey questions were excluded, it is possible that several of the nine remaining respondents similarly misunderstood the survey questions, but did not communicate their interpretation to the authors.

Figure 7: Directed network of direct influence for the technology-push case (Case 2) — Nodes scaled by ANP weights. Visualization generated using Gephi software [20].

Future studies would benefit from a larger sample size and could consider conducting the network influence surveys in-person to better convey instructions to respondents. Sensitivity studies of the network to changes in evaluations would also help clarify the extent to which the final rankings or priorities are affected by uncertainties in the input data or survey findings. Nevertheless, the ANP proved effective in generating a set of weights with applications to future design decision-making regarding the interface.

The ANP offers a powerful method for early-stage design work in order to understand influences and tradeoffs between complex systems, where simpler approaches like the AHP may be unable to capture the full interactions between the systems. In specific cases where decisions will have downstream and even circular influences within the network, the ANP may prove particularly effective at understanding those influences.

5. Future Applications

This research suggests the ANP as a method to understand complex system-integration challenges at an early stage of the design process. Once an expanded network is developed to fully understand the interface between the systems, the method offers significant latitude to the designer to adjust the model to provide information based on varying initial assumptions. The method suggests important prioritizations and allocations of resources, indicating key attributes of the ship and reactor to focus design efforts on in terms of their influence on the overall system. These insights could guide a subsequent design approach. This is especially valuable given the uncertainty surrounding advanced nuclear reactors in the maritime domain. Since the cluster weights can function as a toggle for different assumptions, the designer can revise the network to re-prioritize their decision-making depending on which design drivers are present — for instance, to adapt to designing around a specific reactor in a technology push design scenario — just by adjusting their cluster pairwise comparisons.

Nuclear reactors are conventionally designed to meet specific mission objectives, such as power generation or propulsion. Ship designers take a similar requirements-based approach. The application of the proposed network process is that it could be used both to select a reactor based on assumptions about the marine environment and its application, and, once the reactor is selected, to design the ship to suit the needs of the reactor, or in parallel to the evolving design of the reactor. For example, addressing concerns surrounding motions in a marine environment or safety and containment of radioactive material during interactions with external hazards might require significant and costly alterations to a selected reactor's design. However, understanding how changes to the ship design contribute to addressing these concerns might ease the burden of addressing them internally within the reactor system. As such, the ANP may help to expand the set of feasible reactor solutions for the marine environment or promote a faster integration process. Engaging with this expanded feasible solution space may lead to an improved final ship-reactor combined system or identify latent capabilities that would have otherwise remained undetected.

As alternative designs are considered, they can also be evaluated subject to the priorities output by the active set of assumptions within the design space. This feature offers significant value for decision-making for most methods currently used in the ship design process. For instance, in set-based design, it is necessary to identify dominated solutions for either further improvement or removal [21]. These priorities could offer guidance for identifying dominant or dominated solutions. The subjective comparisons initially used to formulate the network can also be replaced with quantitative data that becomes available later in the design process. This means that, after providing for an initial down-selection between concepts based on available information, the method could be adapted with incoming data to better inform both the evolution of the selected solutions and decision-making between them.

6. Conclusion

This study assessed the use of the Analytical Network Process to develop design priorities by analyzing dependencies within the ship-reactor interface for implementing nuclear reactors in commercial maritime applications. A network linking components of the ship and reactor systems through performance metrics was used. This network implementation effectively represented the interaction between the reactor and ship systems, and the ANP was effective in mapping both direct and indirect dependencies within the network and in producing weights to guide decision-making. The implications of differing assumptions about the network were determined through two case studies, accounting for ship-first (demand-pull) and reactor-first (technology-push) design approaches. In the specific abstraction reviewed, under both sets of assumptions, the external hazard vulnerability of the ship and the space required for the reactor were identified as the most influential performance metrics to target for each system, respectively. These results may guide future design work, but the large variance in survey responses used to assemble the network, combined with the omission of many ship design metrics from this analysis, calls for the collection of additional data and an expansion of the network. Improvements to the survey methodology could yield more accurate results and represent a priority for future work. This study suggests the ANP may be an effective method to understand the effects of combining two or more complex systems and lays the foundation for future research.

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Appendix A: Pairwise Comparisons and Explanations

A1 Influence of Reactor Components on Reactor Components

Influence of reactor components on core configuration (CR = 0.033).

Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Heat Exchange Mechanism	1	1/5 -- As the shielding and containment affect neutron balance in the core, specifically leakage rates, their consideration is much more important than heat exchangers when considering the configuration of the core.	1/9 -- Effective reactivity control is essential for a reactor core and must be prioritized versus heat exchange mechanisms.
Shielding & Containment	5	1	1 -- Neutron balance and transient tolerance are both important considerations for a reactor for both longevity of operation and safety.
Reactivity Control	9	1	1

Influence of reactor components on heat exchange mechanism (CR = 0.033).

Heat Exchange Mechanism	Core Configuration	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	5 -- While shielding and containment materials may limit the design, the configuration of the core is more tightly coupled, in general, to both the design and effectiveness of any heat exchange mechanism.	3 -- Reactivity control will limit fluctuations in thermal power and thus the response requirements of heat exchange, but the configuration of the core informs the ultimate thermal operating conditions of the reactor.
Shielding & Containment	1/5	1	1/3 -- The reactivity control determines the magnitude and rate of thermal transients which the heat exchange mechanisms must respond to.
Reactivity Control	1/3	3	1

Influence of reactor components on reactivity control mechanism.

Reactivity Control	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism
Core Configuration	1	7 -- The design of the reactivity control mechanism is directly coupled to the core design. Thermal feedback is an implicit reactivity control mechanism and is controlled by the heat exchanger, but this factor is considered in core design.
Shielding & Containment	1/7	1

Influence of reactor components on shielding and containment (CR = 0.011).

Shielding & Containment	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	5 -- As shielding and containment are primarily designed to prevent radiation to the environment surrounding the reactor, the choice of core configuration, and therefore the characteristics of radiation, is explicitly more significant in its design.	7 -- During standard operation, the configuration of the core dictates the magnitude and spectrum of the neutron flux emitted from the core. Control mechanisms maintain the steady state of the reactor and activate scram during shutdown events. Thus, during normal operations, the core configuration much more greatly influences the shielding and containment design, while the design of the control mechanism may influence the reactor response time to transient events, requiring a certain amount of overpower tolerance in the shielding.
Heat Exchange Mechanism	1/5	1	1 -- Equal contribution due to roles as transient event tolerators which limit thermal and radiological strain on shielding and containment selections.
Reactivity Control	1/7	1	1

A2 Influence of Reactor Performance on Reactor Components

Influence of reactor performance on core configuration (CR = 0.086).

Core Configuration	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output
Space	1	7 -- Neutron spectra, reaction rates, and leakage are highly sensitive to variations in core size, which thusly constrains configuration of the core. The overall weight of the core only indirectly affects the configuration via material density selections which are themselves chosen for their effect on neutron mean free path.	1/3 -- A well-designed reactor core must prioritize safety during transient events, as well as uptime, often at the expense of size considerations.	1/5 -- A reactor's rated power is directly correlated with the reactor core size. As such, the size of the core must be chosen to fit a desired reactor power level; if vice versa, then the power output of the reactor may be insufficient for fulfilling its deployment mission.
Weight	1/7	1	1/7 -- A heavy reactor that tolerates disruptions and/or has reasonable uptime is acceptable. A light reactor that sacrifices these things is unacceptable.	1/9 -- The weight of the core configuration may be considered when core components are weight-limited (i.e. flowing liquid fuel that requires pumping), but the designed power output is much more informative to the overall core configuration design.
Availability	3	7	1	1/3 -- Availability is a priority in core design, but a reactor must meet design specification in order to fulfill its mission.
Design Power Output	5	9	3	1

Influence of reactor performance on heat exchange mechanism (CR = 0.081).

Heat Exchange Mechanism	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output
Space	1	3 -- As heat exchangers are limited by the surface area exposure of some auxiliary fluid to the reactor core heat source, as well as the bundling and/or dwelling time of the auxiliary fluid in the exchanger, the space of the heat exchange mechanism is by and large more significant than its weight. It is noted that certain working fluids (i.e. liquid metal) require special considerations in pumping power due to increased weight and viscosity which are nonnegligible.	1/7 -- A failure in the heat exchanger that knocks the reactor offline precludes operability. If a choice need be made between high uptime or smaller heat exchanger footprint, the former is the priority.	1/7 -- A proper thermal cycle for achieving the power output design goal is significantly more important than the space the heat exchange mechanism occupies. Heat exchangers by definition should be designed to exchange reactor heat in such a way to meet the power design goal.
Weight	1/3	1	1/5 -- A failure in the heat exchanger that knocks the reactor offline precludes operability. If a choice need be made between high uptime or lighter heat exchanger weight, the former is the priority. This is rated closer to unity versus the above because the weight of the component does have perence to reparability and failure rate.	1/7 -- A proper thermal cycle for achieving the power output design goal is significantly more important than the weight of the heat exchange mechanism. Heat exchangers by definition should be designed to exchange reactor heat in such a way to meet the power design goal.
Availability	7	5	1	1 -- The ability for the heat exchanger to perform its function and the ability for it to meet its design goal criterion are equally significant in the influence of the component selection and design.
Design Power Output	7	7	1	1

Influence of reactor performance on reactivity control mechanism (CR = 0.052).

Reactivity Control	Space	Weight	Availability	Design Power Output
Space	1	1 -- The space occupied by and the weight of any reactivity control mechanisms both impact its effectiveness in controlling the reactor efficiently and quickly in the event of reactivity insertion events.	1/9 -- The reliability of the reactivity control mechanism is paramount to reactor safety and operability.	1/5 -- Reactor power, being directly correlated to reaction rate and core temperature, may affect material selections of the reactivity control mechanism. As such, the space occupied by the control mechanism may need to accomodate thermal expansion in high temperature reactors, but the core power itself informs design decisions more significantly.
Weight	1	1	1/9 -- The reliability of the reactivity control mechanism is paramount to reactor safety and operability.	1/3 -- The weight of a control mechanism is a substantive contributor to its design selection due to its reliance on swift application, however the power output determines operating temperatures and size of the control system. The latter more significantly influences the design.
Availability	9	9	1	9 -- The control mechanism should always be designed first and foremost with reliability and maintainability in mind. No matter the power output, if the control mechanism falters, there can be no reactor.
Design Power Output	5	3	1/9	1

Influence of reactor performance on shielding and containment (CR = 0.056).

Shielding & Containment	Space	Weight	Availability
Space	1	3 -- The primary determination of shielding and containment effectiveness is material density, which is equally affected by weight and space. However, as materials have characteristic densities at operating conditions, the size of the shielding and containment are the independent variable in determining shielding effectiveness.	1/5 -- Shielding is what protects the reactor from disruption and therefore availability will have a strong influence on the design. Space constraints will factor in but not be as driving.
Weight	1/3	1	1/7 -- Constrained weight will be less of a design driver than Availability. Shielding is what protects the reactor from disruptions and therefore availability will have a much more driving influence on the design.
Availability	5	7	1

A3 Influence of Reactor Components on Reactor Performance

Influence of reactor components on availability (CR = 0.059).

Availability	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	1 -- A reactor system is only available to generate power if criticality is maintained, which is determined by fuel composition and reloading cycles. Similarly, power is only retrieved if the heat exchanger is online. A failure in either one of these leads to reactor failure, though for drastically different reasons.	5 -- Generally, the shielding and containment of a reactor are static, barring extreme irradiation or external damage. The core configuration, on the other hand, experiences fuel shuffling and reloading no matter its design (liquid fueled reactors have fuel mixing and online refueling), and must therefore be of greater consideration in terms of reactor availability.	1/7 -- The reactivity control system maintains the relatively steady-state operation of a reactor. The considerations of fuel depletion in the core are long-term effects, while the control mechanism maintains availability constantly.
Heat Exchange Mechanism	1	1	3 -- The heat exchanger informs the reactor availability in the sense that failure in it precludes operation, but the shielding and containment inform the reactor system's tolerance to such failures.	1/5 -- The reactivity control mechanism ensures day-to-day operability of the reactor while the heat exchanger may only fulfill its role if the reactor is operating nominally. Even in the event of a thermal transient, the reactivity control system must be available to shut down the reactor.
Shielding & Containment	1/5	1/3	1	1/9 -- The shielding and containment of the reactor ensure the safety of those near the reactor, the reactivity control mechanism determines whether or not a transient event becomes a disruption.
Reactivity Control	7	5	9	1

Influence of reactor components on space (CR = 0.084).

Space	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	1/7 -- Compared to the heat exchanger, a reactor core is a relatively small contributor to the reactor system's spatial footprint.	1/5 -- The space occupied by a reactor core is defined primarily by the shielding and containment of the core.	3 -- Compared to selections on fuel, moderator, and reflectors, control mechanisms tend to be a smaller contributor to a reactor size. Notably, the implementation of control rods drastically increase the reactor's axial dimension, but the use of control drums, which are likely preferable for ship design, are a much smaller contributor.
Heat Exchange Mechanism	7	1	3 -- A reactor heat exchange mechanism tends to occupy a larger fraction of the reactor footprint.	7 -- Heat exchangers tend to occupy much more space than control mechanisms due to fluid dependencies.
Shielding & Containment	5	1/3	1	3 -- While the control elements themselves do not occupy much space (i.e. AP1000, VHTGR), the mechanisms that drive them can contribute significantly to the size of the reactor system. The dominance of the shielding and containment over the control mechanism of choice varies, but is generally substantially larger in terms of spatial importance.
Reactivity Control	1/3	1/7	1/3	1

Influence of reactor components on weight (CR = 0.063).

Weight	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Shielding & Containment	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	1/5 -- While the heat exchange mechanism tends to be much larger and heavier than a reactor core, a substantive amount of heavy metal and structural material is contained within the reactor core, making it relatively materially dense.	1/3 -- Need for shielding and containment scales directly with core size, with their overall thicknesses outside the core being pertinent to safety. As such, very large reactor cores may contribute more drastically to the reactor's weight, but the shielding and containment generally dominate.	5 -- The primary means of controlling a reactor involve light element absorbers such as B-10. As such, the weight of the reactor system is much more influenced by the heavy metals in the fissile regions than by the control elements.
Heat Exchange Mechanism	5	1	3 -- While a heat exchange mechanism generally exceeds the shielding and containment in terms of footprint, the heavy materials necessary for radiation protection make it a non-trivial contributor to the weight of the reactor system.	9 -- For much the same rationale as for the space performance metric, the heat exchanger selection contributes much more drastically to the weight of the reactor system simply due to its generally larger size versus any modern control mechanism.
Shielding & Containment	3	1/3	1	7 -- The heavy materials required to absorb and retain radiation and radiological damages, as well as the generally greater size of the shielding and containment, make it a much greater contributor to the weight of the reactor versus the control mechanism.
Reactivity Control	1/5	1/9	1/7	1

Influence of reactor components on design power output (CR = 0.000).

Design Power Output	Core Configuration	Heat Exchange Mechanism	Reactivity Control
Core Configuration	1	1 -- The thermal power generated in the reactor is directly correlated with the size and style of the core configuration, but the heat exchange mechanism is the sole means of converting thermal power to electric power. Efficient heat exchangers may reduce the need for large or complicated cores and vice versa.	3 -- Achieving the designed thermal power output threshold is the role of the core configuration, but while power is generated in the core, the reactivity control mechanism determines how a reactor responds to startup, shutdown, and under/overpower transient events.
Heat Exchange Mechanism	1	1	3 -- The efficiency in converting thermal power to electrical power is crucial to the reactor design. The reactivity control mechanism ensures the swings in the thermal power output, and thus the electrical power output, are low.
Reactivity Control	1/3	1/3	1

A4 Influence of Ship Components on Reactor Performance

Space	Hull Shape	Structure
Hull Shape	1	7 -- Hull shape is fundamentally spatial. Structure may have some impact in terms of permissible weight distribution.
Structure	1/7	1

Weight	Hull Shape	Structure
Hull Shape	1	1/5 -- Structure, especially locally, is more sensitive to weight, and is also relevant from a global bending perspective. Meanwhile, hull shape is only impacted globally and in terms of displacement, which will likely be less sensitive than structures, especially locally.
Structure	5	1

Influence of ship components on space.

Influence of ship components on weight.

A5 Influence of Reactor Performance on Ship Components

Influence of reactor performance on power generation (CR = 0.056).

Power Generation	Space	Availability	Design Power Output
Space	1	1/5 -- Space impacts power generation only through arrangements, while availability (or lack thereof) will impact choices about secondary generation power systems substantially.	1/7 -- Space impacts only through arrangements, while design power output will directly impact choice of primary power conversion system.
Availability	5	1	1/5 -- Design power output is the main driver of primary systems, while availability is main driver of secondary systems.
Design Power Output	7	5	1

Hull Shape	Space	Weight
Space	1	5 -- Weight drives displacement & stability, but space is more important for determining shape characteristics.
Weight	1/5	1

Influence of reactor performance on hull shape.

Structure	Space	Weight
Space	1	1/5 --Space will influence the weight distribution, but weight will directly drive structural design, both locally and for global bending.
Weight	5	1

Influence of reactor performance on ship structure.

A6 Influence of Ship Components on Ship Components

Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation
Structure	1	5 -- Engines may require provision of additional space in hull shape design, but, if certain structures are required for ship system (i.e. protective structural layers around a reactor), they may force changes to the hull.
Power Generation	1/5	1

Influence of ship components on hull shape.

Structure	Hull Shape	Power Generation
Hull Shape	1	5 -- Power generation creates point loads contributing to global bending and local loading but hull shape drives global bending forces through influences on buoyant force, and determines local impact forces during operation in different conditions.
Power Generation	1/5	1

Influence of ship components on ship structure.

A7 Influence of Ship Performance on Ship Components

Influence of ship performance on hull shape (CR = 0.000).

Hull Shape	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand
External Hazard Vulnerability	1	1/5 -- Larger dimensions allow more room for structure, but motions performance is directly driven by hull shape. A larger vessel may also be a bigger target.	1/5 -- Power demand requirements / constraints can rapidly limit hull shape options, whereas vulnerabilities will indirectly expand structural options.
Motions Susceptibility	5	1	1 -- Tradeoffs between two major drivers of hull shape.
Power Demand	5	1	1

Influence of ship performance on power generation (CR = 0.025).

Power Generation	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand
External Hazard Vulnerability	1	3 -- Vulnerabilities will influence decisions about redundancy and siting of equipment. Motions will influence auxiliary systems, but likely only slightly.	1/5 -- Power demand is significantly more important for power generation, but vulnerabilities will have some influence, especially in terms of arrangements of power generation systems & redundancy.
Motions Susceptibility	1/3	1	1/9 -- Power demand is overwhelmingly more important. Any motions impacts are only tangentially influential.
Power Demand	5	9	1

Influence of ship performance on structure (0.069).

Structure	External Hazard Vulnerability	Motions Susceptibility	Power Demand
External Hazard Vulnerability	1	7 -- Motions constraints will influence center of gravity of structure, but structure is a not driving influence on VCG. Structure will have to withstand motions effects. However, structure is absolutely essential to extraordinary event vulnerability, and setting a vulnerability requirement will have overwhelming influence on structure.	9 -- Countering vulnerabilities will have overwhelmingly more influence on structure.
Motions Susceptibility	1/7	1	3 -- Motions will have limited influence through center of gravity and requirements for structure to withstand accelerations, whereas constrained power demand may only slightly impact choices about structural design.
Power Demand	1/9	1/3	1

A8 Influence of Ship Components on Ship Performance

Influence of ship components on external hazard vulnerability (CR = 0.06).

External Hazard Vulnerability	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation
Hull Shape	1	1/7 -- Structure is the primary means of protection but hull shape will have some influence.	1/3 -- Hull shape has limited impact by influencing arrangements, but power generation has key influence through siting and redundancies.
Structure	7	1	5 -- Redundancies are important but structure is primary means of defense.
Power Generation	3	1/5	1

Influence of ship components on motions susceptibility (CR = 0.000).

Motions Susceptibility	Hull Shape	Structure	Power Generation
Hull Shape	1	7 -- Hull shape is driving determining factor, whereas structure only has limited impact through center of gravity.	7 -- Hull shape is driving determining factor, whereas power generation only has limited impact through center of gravity.
Structure	1/7	1	1 -- Both only influence through center of gravity.
Power Generation	1/7	1	1

A9 Case 1 Cluster Weighting Pairwise Comparisons

Clusters weighted for ship performance influence (CR = 0.003).

Ship Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	1/7 -- Ship performance impacts will be tangential; ship components directly drive performance.	1/3 -- The reactor functions as a component of the ship -- it is going to be significantly more influential than tangential impacts from other ship performance metrics, although not as much as all of the ship components put together.	1/3 Component impacts will function as a fraction of the overall contributions to each performance metric, but choices about components will be essential to target each metric.
Ship Components	7	1	3 -- Reactor functions as a component.	3 -- Components together define operating profile of ship and operate as a system. 1 -- Components can directly interface with ship performance, for instance contributing to reduced vulnerability to external hazards through separation of systems and redundancy, but can also act through their performance.
Reactor Performance	3	1/3	1	
Reactor Components	3	1/3	1	1

Clusters weighted for ship components influence (CR = 0.000).

Ship Components	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance
Ship Performance	1	5 -- Ship components influence each other through tradeoffs and requirements for compatibility. However, objectives are the primary driver of decisions about ship components, and different components can be chosen to meet compatibility requirements after decisions necessary to meet performance requirements.	5 -- Under assumptions, ship performance is primary priority, but defense in depth and ensuring basic functionality are still important and will influence decisions about ship components.
Ship Components	1/5	1	1 -- Both are tangential drivers of ship component decisions under assumptions, only driving to ensure compatibility.
Reactor Performance	1/5	1	1

Clusters weighted for reactor performance influence (CR = 0.011).

Reactor Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	5 -- Ship performance sets objectives for the reactor while components will function as constraints. However, components are more adaptive than ship performance, so while limiting, they will be less driving than the objective. Further, ship performance was emphasized as key objective in terms of meeting requirements.	1 -- While ship performance sets objectives for the reactor, reactor components will be the primary drivers of the reactor's operation. Under the stated assumptions, however, the reactor design must adapt to meet performance needs, so deficiencies of reactor performance will primarily be addressed by alternative component decisions, reducing their constraining influence.
Ship Components	1/5	1	1/7 -- Reactor components are the primary drivers of reactor performance. Ship component impacts are tangential, acting only as limited constraints.
Reactor Components	1	7	1

Clusters weighted for reactor components influence (CR = 0.056).

Reactor Components	Ship Performance	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	1/5 -- Ship performance defines operating conditions, functioning as constraints, but reactor performance has direct influence on reactor components and is the primary means by which they are influenced.	3 -- Both function as constraints, influencing decisions made about reactor components. However, assuming the prioritization of ship performance increases willingness to accept tradeoffs with reactor components, so ship performance is moderately more important.
Reactor Performance	5	1	7 -- Reactor performance defines direct objectives for reactor components while reactor components only force tradeoffs to ensure compatibility.
Reactor Components	1/3	1/7	1

A10 Case 2 Cluster Weighting Pairwise Comparisons

Clusters weighted for ship performance influence (CR = 0.005).

Ship Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	1/7 -- Performance has tangential impacts but components are key driver.	1/5 -- Willingness to accept ship performance tradeoffs under these assumptions makes the performance of the reactor more determining in terms of influence on ship performance.	1/5 -- Willingness to accept ship performance tradeoffs under these assumptions makes the components of the reactor more important in terms of influence on ship performance.
Ship Components	7	1	1 -- Performance directly impacted by ship components and reactor functions as a component so equally forcing in this case given assumptions.	1 -- Ship performance directly impacted by reactor components; while reactor components are more restricted, so these clusters are equally forcing in this case despite representing only one component of the total ship system.
Reactor Performance	5	1	1	1 -- Reactor components and performance both drive ship performance significantly.
Reactor Components	5	1	1	1

Clusters weighted for ship components influence (CR = 0.000).

Ship Components	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Performance
Ship Performance	1	5 -- Performance sets objectives, but components constrain each other and force tradeoffs.	1 -- Normally ship performance is driving, but under the stated assumptions the reactor strongly constrains choices about ship components.
Ship Components	1/5	1	1/5 -- The reactor is the primary source of constraints on the ship components in this case. Tradeoffs between ship components are more negotiable under the stated assumptions.
Reactor Performance	1	5	1

Clusters weighted for reactor performance influence (CR = 0.000).

Reactor Performance	Ship Performance	Ship Components	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	1 -- Ship Performance sets objectives and components constraints, but the stated assumptions mean neither is driving the reactor design.	1/9 -- Reactor components are the primary determining factor under the stated assumptions.
Ship Components	1	1	1/9 -- Reactor components are the primary determining factor under the stated assumptions.
Reactor Components	9	9	1

Clusters weighted for reactor components influence (CR = 0.023).

Reactor Components	Ship Performance	Reactor Performance	Reactor Components
Ship Performance	1	1/7 -- Reactor performance is the primary driver of reactor component decisions in absence of other factors given the reactor-first assumption, but ship performance may have limited impacts on some components.	1/5 -- Reactor components constrain reactor design, while ship performance has little bearing, but may motivate small alterations, also acting as a constraint, albeit less strictly.
Reactor Performance	7	1	1 -- Both influence selection of reactor components, in different ways.
Reactor Components	5	1	1

Appendix B: The Ship-Reactor Interface Survey

Pairwise comparison survey as it was displayed to respondents.

0%

100%

This survey aims to explore the **interface between ships/marine platforms and nuclear reactors** to support research into nuclear applications for maritime use. You will be asked to perform **pairwise comparisons** between different elements within this interface with regard to their influence on other elements of the interface.

This survey has a limited scope and does not cover the full interface. For now, our study excludes some important aspects such as regulatory considerations and personnel and environmental risks. Instead, our goal is to validate our methodology for mapping the network between ship and reactor systems.

When answering the survey questions, consider them from the standpoint of design choices. For example, if choices about the design of reactor core cooling mechanisms could result in significant sensitivity to ship motions during normal operations—meaning that the cooling mechanism would be a key design element in determining tolerance to accelerations, inclinations, or vibrations—then you would indicate that the design of the cooling system **contributes more to the reactor's susceptibility to motions than another system for which design choices would have less impact on the acceptable range of motions.**

1. Please indicate which category(ies) best describe your affiliation with nuclear for maritime. Select all that apply.

Nuclear Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maritime Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>
Governmental	<input type="checkbox"/>
Non-Governmental Organization	<input type="checkbox"/>
Environmental Group	<input type="checkbox"/>
Energy Sector	<input type="checkbox"/>
Shipbuilding	<input type="checkbox"/>
Research & Development	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulator	<input type="checkbox"/>
Academia	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

What other affiliations with nuclear for maritime do you have?

2. Please **compare the relative contributions of design choices about each pair of reactor components below** to the **vulnerability** of the reactor and its interdependent systems to external physical disruptions causing damage, such as **an external object impacting the plant and damaging plant systems**. **Vulnerability** in this context refers to the likelihood that damage from external hazards to the ship like collisions, allisions, or groundings will result in non-operability or unsafe conditions of the system (ship + reactor). Examples of damage from these hazards are direct impulse forces against components or transferred impacts via deformation of other components, failures of components elsewhere in the system, fires, and flooding.

Example: Consider a large aircraft's vulnerability to bird strikes. Engine design contributes vastly more to the likelihood of a bird strike causing a crash or forcing the aircraft out of operation than the design of the seats used in the plane. Therefore, if considering a **pairwise comparison** between the contributions of **choices about the engine design and the seat design** to vulnerability, a reviewer assessing this question might indicate a contribution of **9** on the side of the engine, indicating the **relative** significance of the engine design in this context.

Definitions -- As you respond to this question, please utilize the following definitions of reactor components:

1. Core Configuration: The materials and design of the physical entity producing self-sustaining fission reactions, not including cooling or control systems. This includes the fuel, reflector, any moderator, and necessary structural materials that impact neutronic considerations.
2. Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanisms: Any pumps, pipes, or other structures necessary for heating/cooling the core, maintaining reactor operating temperatures, and transmitting thermal power to external electrical/mechanical power conversion devices.
3. Shielding & Containment: Any mechanisms or components that protect the reactor from external factors or contain the release of radioactive materials in the event of an accident, as well as the radiation shielding necessary to protect operators and external systems.
4. Reactivity Control: The mechanisms whose sole or supplementary purpose is the adjustment of reactor criticality, such as control rods, drums, or poisons.

	Extremely More Contributing 9	Contributing Very Much More 7	Contributing Much More 5	Contributing Moderately More 3	Contributing Equally 1	Contributing Moderately More 3	Contributing Much More 5	Contributing Very Much More 7	Extremely More Contributing 9	
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Shielding & Containment
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control
Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Shielding & Containment
Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control
Shielding & Containment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control

3. Please **compare the relative contributions of design choices about each pair of reactor components below** to the **susceptibility** of the reactor and its interdependent systems to **motions occurring during normal operating conditions** such as **accelerations** of varying magnitudes, frequencies, and directions, or **inclinations** to various angles along any degree of freedom.

Example: Consider a car moving on a bumpy road. The suspension system contributes a lot more to mitigating the bumpiness experienced by the passengers than the design of the engine. In a **pairwise comparison** between these two components with regard to influence on the car's performance on bumpy roads, a reviewer might assign a contribution of **7** on the side of **design choices about** the suspension, indicating the **relative** significance of the suspension design in this context.

Definitions -- As you respond to this question, please utilize the following definitions of reactor components:

1. Core Configuration: The materials and design of the physical entity producing self-sustaining fission reactions, not including cooling or control systems. This includes the fuel, reflector, any moderator, and necessary structural materials that impact neutronic considerations.
2. Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanisms: Any pumps, pipes, or other structures necessary for heating/cooling the core, maintaining reactor operating temperatures, and transmitting thermal power to external electrical/mechanical power conversion devices. This does not include the power conversion devices themselves.
3. Shielding & Containment: Any mechanisms or components that protect the reactor from external factors or contain the release of radioactive materials in the event of an accident, as well as the radiation shielding necessary to protect operators and external systems.
4. Reactivity Control: The mechanisms whose sole or supplementary purpose is the adjustment of reactor criticality, such as control rods, drums, or poisons.

	Extremely More Contributing 9	Contributing Very Much More 7	Contributing Much More 5	Contributing Moderately More 3	Contributing Equally 1	Contributing Moderately More 3	Contributing Much More 5	Contributing Very Much More 7	Extremely More Contributing 9	
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Shielding & Containment
Core Configuration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control
Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Shielding & Containment
Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control
Shielding & Containment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Reactivity Control

0%

100%

The following questions ask you to **rank the relative influence** of two performance metrics of the ship on your **design choices about reactor components**. Specifically, they ask you to consider, for each component, whether the **threat of damage** from identified hazards impacting the ship **outside of normal operations** (External Hazard Vulnerability), or **motions during normal vessel operations** would have more influence on your design and/or choices regarding various reactor components.

For example: Consider the suspension of a car, the primary purpose of which is to reduce the motions experienced by the car's occupants. Therefore, when evaluating factors likely to influence the suspension's design, the terrain the car is expected to operate in would likely have **much more influence on** the design of the suspension of most cars than the rate at which it is intended to be able to turn. Therefore, a reviewer considering this question might select a preference of **5** on the side of terrain in a **pairwise comparison** between terrain and turning rate with regard to their **relative influence** on vehicle suspension.

In your responses, please consider the following definitions as they apply to the reactor system:

1. External Hazard Vulnerability: The likelihood that damage from external hazards to the ship like collisions, allisions, or groundings will result in non operability or unsafe conditions of the system (ship + reactor). Examples of damage from these hazards are direct impulse forces against components or transferred impacts via deformation of other components, failures of components elsewhere in the system, fires, and flooding.
2. Motions: Accelerations of varying magnitudes, frequencies, and directions, or inclinations to various angles along any degree of freedom, occurring during normal operation (i.e. design conditions) of the ship and reactor systems.

4. When considering alternative reactor designs, which factor would have a **greater influence** on your **design and/or choice of Core Configuration**, defined as the materials and design of the physical entity producing self-sustaining fission reactions, not including cooling or control systems? This includes the fuel, reflector, any moderator, and necessary structural materials that impact neutronic considerations.

	Extremely More Influence 9	Very Much More Influence 7	Much More Influence 5	Moderately More Influence 3	Equal Influence 1	Moderately More Influence 3	Much More Influence 5	Very Much More Influence 7	Extremely More Influence 9	
External Hazard Vulnerability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Motions

5. When considering alternative reactor designs, which factor would have a **greater influence** on your **design and/or choice of Heat Exchange / Removal Mechanisms**, defined as any pumps, pipes, or other structures necessary for **heating/cooling the core**, **maintaining reactor operating temperatures**, and **transmitting thermal power** to external electrical/mechanical power conversion devices. This does not include the power conversion devices themselves.

	Extremely More Influence 9	Very Much More Influence 7	Much More Influence 5	Moderately More Influence 3	Equal Influence 1	Moderately More Influence 3	Much More Influence 5	Very Much More Influence 7	Extremely More Influence 9	
External Hazard Vulnerability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Motions

6. When considering alternative reactor designs, which factor would have a **greater influence** on your **design of Shielding & Containment** for the reactor, defined as any mechanisms or components that protect the reactor from external factors or contain the release of radioactive materials in the event of an accident, as well as the radiation shielding necessary to protect operators and external systems.

	Extremely More Influence 9	Very Much More Influence 7	Much More Influence 5	Moderately More Influence 3	Equal Influence 1	Moderately More Influence 3	Much More Influence 5	Very Much More Influence 7	Extremely More Influence 9	
External Hazard Vulnerability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Motions

7. When considering alternative reactor designs, which factor would have a **greater influence** on your **design and/or choice of Reactivity Control** mechanisms for the reactor, defined as the mechanisms whose sole or supplementary purpose is the adjustment of reactor criticality, such as control rods, drums, or poisons.

	Extremely More Influence 9	Very Much More Influence 7	Much More Influence 5	Moderately More Influence 3	Equal Influence 1	Moderately More Influence 3	Much More Influence 5	Very Much More Influence 7	Extremely More Influence 9	
External Hazard Vulnerability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Motions

8. Optional: In addition to external hazard vulnerability and ship motions, please state what you view as the most important single other consideration from ship design and/or operations that would impact reactor operations or components.

Which reactor operations or components would this consideration most impact?

